

SOME HISTORICAL ASPECTS ABOUT THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGINEERING GEOLOGY

The following is a sequence of data seeking to reflect the evolution of Engineering Geology knowledge, grouped into periods that contemplate significant advances and/or important changes, either in the increment of knowledge or in the approach form. Table 1 shows the main books, technical-scientific publications, technical events and historical facts in Engineering Geology.

Table 1. Special books, technical-scientific publications, technical events and historical facts that brought new perspectives to the teaching of Engineering Geology.

(This table does not contemplate all the events that constitute the History of Engineering Geology, but those that were fundamental for the elaboration of the text.)

Year/Period	Author/Country/Institutions	Books, technical-scientific publications, technical events and facts that brought new perspectives to the teaching of Engineering Geology.
1452-1519	Leonardo de Vinci	Considered the first practitioner of “applied geology” for engineering works”
1556	Georg Bauer (Georgius Agrícola)	Book: De Re Metallica
1725	John Strachey	Presented Cross sections of the Somerset coal mine. (First application of Geology to human activities). Strachey (1725).
1776	John Smeaton	First used the name Civil Engineering (First registration) Morris (2003)
1778	John Whitehurst	He presented Cross sections of the Derbyshire mining region.
1795	James Hutton, Scotland	Theory of the Earth (Distinguished the 3 rock types)
1799/1801/ 1815	William Smith	Geological map for mining (coal) and engineering (channels) purposes. Considered by many scholars as the first Engineering Geologist.
1830	Charles Lyell	Principles of Geology
1838	William W. Mather USA	Rotational slides lake front at Cleveland
1839	James Hall USA	Classification of excavation rock, Erie Canal
1862	F.A. Fallou	Pedology - Saxony
1870/1880	Dokuchaiev	Pedology - Russia
1880	Pennings	First book of Engineering geology
1880	Mahan	A treatise on Civil Engineering
1888	USA	Engineering Geology Division was established at the Geological Society of America in the United States
1890	USA	Pioneering work by William O. Crosbi, James F. Kemp
1893	William O. Crosbi	Introduction of geologic concepts in the planning

		of public works in Boston. Considered the Father of the Engineering Geology of USA.
1897/1906	Woodward	Elaboration of the Subsoil map of London
1906	D.W. Johnson USA	Application of geology to various uses of mankind and engineering structures
1908	Charles Lapworth (1842–1920)	The principle of Engineering geology. Lecture in the Institution of Civil Engineers.
1910	England	Beginning of Engineering Geology teaching at Imperial College (England)
1911	C.Lapworth, H. Lapworth	The geology of dam trenches.
1913	USA	Book: Mineral Deposits (Engineering geology practice)
1913	Langen (Germany)	Building Technical Exhibition: Engineering geological charts and maps to support the development of the cities of Erfurt, Frankfurt, Danzig.
1914	Ries, Watson	Publication of second book of Engineering geology
1919	L. V. Pirsson	Rock classification for Engineering
1921	Watson Ries	Book: Elements of Engineering Geology
1922	Josef Stini (Austria)	Technische Geologie (Engineering geology)
1920-1930	Russia	Maps and charts in support of the construction of the canal between the White Sea and the Baltic Sea and the Volga Right Bank Irrigation Project.
1925	K. Terzaghi	First book of Soil mechanics - Erdbaumechanik auf bodenphysikalischer Grundlage. Deuticke, Wien.
1926	Ex-Checoslováquia	Engineering geology maps to support the development of the city of Prague
1927	I. Popov	Creation and development of engineering-geologic pedology in Russia
Antes de 1928	Charles Berkey	First Engineering Geology course - Columbia. First geologist hired as Engineering Geologist by USBR
1928	USA	St. Francis Dam in California collapses and 426 people die.
1929	K. Terzaghi	"Effect of Minor Geologic Details on the Safety of Dams "
1929	Redlich, Terzaghi and Kampe	Book – Engineering geology. Three chapters (250 of 680 pages of text) in "Ingenieurgeologie"
1934	Rússia	General engineering geological map for Russia
1935	C.S.Fox	Book: A comprehensive treatise on Engineering Geology.
1936	Polônia	Engineering geological maps to support the development of the city of Warsaw.
1936	IASMF	First International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering
1938	USA	Terzaghi starting the engineering geology at Harvard university (Suggestions for a Course in Engineering Geology).
1939	Legget, Boswell	Geology and Engineering
1941	I. Popov	Fundamentals of engineering-geologic pedology and Soil characteristics and selection of soils for engineering-geologic investigations.
1943	Blyth	Geology for Engineer
1947	Zebera	Geologie in der regionalenplanung. Geotechnica,

		vol. 4, Praha. Proposed the Method of bands for 3D representation.
1947	George A. Kiersch	Founding of the Engineering Geology Division as the first operating division of the Geological Society of America
1947	Hans Cloos (Scale model)	<i>Gespräch mit der Erde</i> , 1947; translated into English as <i>Conversations with the Earth</i> by E.B. Garside, 1953.
1947	K. Terzaghi	Book: Engineering Geology
1950	I. Popov (Ex-URSS)	Book "Techniques for the elaboration of Engineering geological Maps".
1949/1950	S. Paige	Berkey Volume – Application of Geology to Engineering Practices (Geological Society)
1951	Executive Committee of the Division on Engineering Geology of the Geological Society of America	First conceptualization of the Engineering Geology professional.
1951	Eckel	Interpreting of geologic maps for engineers
1952	Milan Matula	Comenius University in Bratislava created the Department of Engineering Geology, within Czechoslovakia,
1954	Gwinner	Engineering geological/Geotechnical Unit Concept
1955	J.R.Schultz, A.B.Cleaves	Geology in Engineering
1955	Karl Terzaghi	"The Influence of Geologic Factors on the Engineering Properties of Sediments"
1957	USA	Association of Engineering Geologists (USA)
1957	Krynine and Judd	Principles of Engineering Geology and Geotechnics
1957	K. Terzaghi	Engineering Geology
1957	I.V. Popov	Theoretical fundamentals of the engineering-geologic classification of rocks.
1958	I.V. Popov	Significance of the investigations of formations in engineering geology.
1962	R.F. Legget	Geology and Engineering. 2nd Edition.
1962	R.C.D Walters	Dam geology
1963	Parker D. Trask; George A. Kiersch	GSA engineering geology case histories. Engineering Geology Case Histories Number 4
1963	Q. Zaruba, V.Mencl	Engineering Geology". Elsevier, Amsterdam.
1964	J. E. Richey	Elements of Engineering Geology
1964	Europe	Beginning of the International Association of Engineering Geology
1964	England	Founding of the Engineering Geology Group at the Geological Society
1965/1966	COMECON	Instructions for preparing unified engineering geology maps
1965	G.A. Kiersch	The Vaiont Tragedy: geologic causes and engineering implications.
1966	Peter (France)	Essai de Carte géotechnique
1967	Bachmann et al. (Germany Democratic Republic)	"Instruktion für die Anfertigung einheitlicher Ingenieurgeolo-

		gischer Gründ-karten”.
1967	ISRM	First Congress of the International Society of Rock Mechanics
1968	Malkovsky, Záruba	Engineering Geology in Country Planning
1968	CSIRO	Proposed the P.U.C.E system
1969	Matula	Regional Engineering Geology of Czechoslovak Carpathians
1970	IAEG (Paris)	1st International Congress of Engineering Geology - Paris
1970	Thomas	Réflexion sur la cartographie géotechnique 1970/1971
1972	Report by the Geological Society Engineering Group Working Party(Grã Bretanha)	The preparation of maps and plans in terms of engineering geology
1972	Sanejouand (Ministère de l'Équipement et Du Logement-France)	La Cartographie Gèotechnique en France
1974	ABGE/IAEG (São Paulo)	2nd International Congress of Engineering Geology – São Paulo
1974	Varnes	The logic of engineering geological and related maps. A discussion of the definition and classification of map units, with special references to problems presented by maps intended for uses in civil engineering
1976	G. Zaruba, V. Mencl	Engineering Geology
1976	IAEG	Guide to preparation of Engineering Geological Maps
1976	P. B. Attewell & I. W. Farmer	Principles Of Engineering Geology
1978	IAEG	3rd International Congress of Engineering Geology - Madrid
1979	IAEG (United Kingdom)	“Engineering Geological Mapping Symposium”, Newcastle upon Tyne.
1979	IAEG (Commission Engineering Geological Mapping)	Classification of Rocks and Soils for Engineering Geological Mapping. Part 1: Rock and Soil Materials.
1982	IAEG	Land Surface Evaluation for Engineering Practice
1982	Report by a Working Party under the auspices of the Geological Society	Land Surface Evaluation for Engineering Practice
1986	IAEG	5th International Congress of Engineering Geology – Buenos Aires
1988	Paul G. Marinos , George C. Koukis	Engineering Geology and the Protection of Historical Sites and Monuments (The Engineering Geology of Ancient Works, Monuments and Historical Sites: Preservation and Protection, Vol.1 1st Edition
1988	Robert B. Johnson, Jerome V. DeGraff.	Principles of engineering geology
1990	IAEG	6th International Congress of Engineering Geology - Amsterdam
1991	G.A.Kiersch	The heritage of Engineering Geology: The First hundred years.

1991	Dearman (United Kingdom)	Book: Engineering Geological Mapping.
1993	F.G. Bell	Book: Engineering geology
1995	Milan Matula	“Engineering Geology in Land-use Planning.
1997	Fookes	First Glossop Lecture - Geology for engineers:the geological model, prediction and performance.
1998	A.M.S.Oliveira, S.N.A.Brito,	Engineering Geology Book in Portuguese (ABGE)
1998	Engineering Geology Group (US Department of the Interior – Bureaux of Reclamation)	Engineering Geology Field Manual
2000	Morgenstern (Australia)	Proposal of the term Common Ground
2002	Knill	Core values: the first Hans Cloos Lecture.
2004	JEWG - Europe	Concepts of Ground Engineering (Engineering Geology for Infrastructure Planning in EuropeA European Perspective)
2005	Proske, Vlcko, Rosenbaum, Dorn, Culshaw, Marker (Report of IAEG Commission 1 Engineering Geology Mapping)	Special purpose mapping for waste disposal sites.
2005	M.G. Culshaw	From concept towards reality: developing the attributed3D geological model of the shallow subsurface
2006	H. Bock	Common ground in engineering geology, soil mechanics and rock mechanics: past, present and future
2006	IAEGE (England)	10th International Congress of Engineering Geology
2006	Chacón, Irigaray, Fernández, El Hamdouni	Engineering geology maps: landslide and geographical information systems. Report to the Commission 1 on Engineering Geology Maps, IAEGE
2006	Alan E. Kehew	Geology for Engineers and Environmental Scientists
2008	Michael de Freitas (Compilador, Editor), David George Price (Autor)	Engineering Geology: Principles and Practice
2008	Culshaw, Reeves and Rosenbaum	Two hundred years engineering geology
2009	H. Bock	Core values, competences and issues in engineering geology: a European perspective
2010	IAEG	11th International Congress of Engineering Geology - Auckland
2011	Luis Gonzalez de Vallejo, Mercedes Ferrer	Geological Engineering
2011	P.T.Sawant	Engineering and General Geology
2011	P. C. Varghese	Engineering geology for civil engineers
2011	Syed E. Hasan, Benedetto De Vivo, Bernhard Grasemann, Kurt Stüwe, Jan Lastovicka, Syed M. Hasan, Chen Yong (EDS)	Environmental and Engineering Geology
2012	Steve Hencher	Practical Engineering Geology
2013	Subinoy Gangopadhyay	Engineering Geology

2014	S. Parry, F. J. Baynes, M. G. Culshaw, M. Eggers, J. F. Keaton, K. Lentfer, J. Novotny & D. Paul	Engineering geological models: an introduction: IAEG commission 25
2015	Fookes, Pettifer, Waltham	Geomodels in Engineering Geology: An Introduction
2016	M. J. Eggers; J. S. Griffiths; S. Parry; M. G. Culshaw	Developments in Engineering Geology
2016	D.V Ready	Engineering Geology
2016	Fletcher, C. J.	Geology for ground engineering projects
2016	James H. Williams	Engineering Geology – Definitions and Historical Development Applications in Life Support Systems
2016	M.J. Egger	Diversity in the science and practice of engineering geology
2017	Nurcihan Ceryan (Balikesir University, Turkey)	Handbook of Research on Trends and Digital Advances in Engineering Geology
2018	Peter T. Bobrowsky, Brian Marker	Encyclopedia of Engineering Geology
2020	K.M. Bangar	Principals of Engineering Geology
2021	Qing Yang, Dong-Sheng Jeng, Xiaolei Liu et al., Eds.	New Advances in Marine Engineering Geology
2021	Edited by Essa Lwisa and Hasan Arman	Engineering Geology
2022	BGS	Significant opportunity' for engineering geologists to increase influence on global sustainable development
2022	IAEGE	Best practice on use of engineering geological models
2022	Richard Lagesse, Jennifer Hambling, Joel Gill, Marcus Dobbs, Cheryl Lim and Peter Ingvorsen	The role of engineering geology in delivering the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
2023	James S Griffiths , F G Bell	Environmental and Engineering Geology: Beyond the Basics
2023	IAEGE Congress	Engineering Geology for a Habitable Earth

XVIII/ XIX CENTURY

In this period, some activities occurred that demonstrated the use of the knowledge of Engineering Geology. John Strachey, in 1725, developed work in the Somerset mine (England) and a set of vertical cross sections to assist in planning the opening and excavation. And John Whitehurst presented similar work for the Derbyshire mines in 1778. James Hutton (Scotland) published, in 1795, the book "Theory of the Earth," in which he distinguished the 3 rock types known to date, becoming a landmark for Geology and, consequently, for Engineering Geology.

Between 1799 and 1815, William Smith developed several works in England. He prepared a geological map to guide the implementation of canals (<http://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/IOTD/view.php?id=8733>), considered the first Engineering geological Map and the emergence of the term and the science of Engineering Geology. In 1830 and 1833, two parallel works appeared that supported Geology and Engineering Geology, one being the publication of "Principles of Geology," by Charles Lyell and the other, the book "Treatise on Road," by H.B. Parnell, which presents a group of conditions of the geological materials that must be considered for the construction of slopes in roads.

Two works published in the USA are important: William W. Mather, in 1838, published work on rotational slides in a lake in the Cleveland area and, in 1839, James Hall proposed a classification for rock excavation, which was applied in the construction of the Erie Canal.

F. A. Fallou (Saxony) and, probably between 1870 and 1880, V.V. Dokuchaiev and N.M. Sibertsev (Russia) published texts on Pedology, bringing ideas about the concept of soil, involving aspects of dynamics and morphology, among others, that last until today. In this same period, the concepts of erosion and the main gravitational mass movements were proposed, which are still valid today.

The most important point in this period was the release of the first Engineering Geology book, in 1889/1880, by W. H. Penning (Engineering Geology), with chapters that portrayed the different knowledge and steps involved in an Engineering Geology investigation and a set of applications. In this same period, the book by Mahan (1880) - A treatise on Civil Engineering, was published, which addresses, in several chapters, the contents of geological knowledge related to foundations and construction materials.

XX CENTURY

During this century, a wider spread of Engineering Geology occurred. It is possible to define some periods, such as between 1900 and 1950 when it occurred predominantly in North American countries and Europe, and after 1950 when it spread to Latin American, African, Asian, and Oceania countries.

Period between 1900 and 1925.

The post-breakup evaluation of the Austin dam (Texas - USA) in 1900 concluded that failure occurred due to geological constraints. From the end of the 19th century, from 1897 to around

1906, several versions of the London Subsoil map intended to guide the planning of sanitation works were presented by Woodward. In 1906, D.W. Johnson (USA) published a text on applying Geology to various human activities and engineering structures. He was followed, in 1908, by Charles Lapworth's work with Principles of Engineering Geology in the form of two Lectures at the Institution of Civil Engineers (Imperial College), London.

The teaching of Engineering Geology began in 1910 at Imperial College (England) as a regular subject. In 1911, Charles Lapworth published texts on Applied Geology for Dams, and R. F. Sorsbie published the book "Geology for Engineers," which presented very advanced Engineering Geology content for the time.

In 1913, the text "Mineral Deposits (Engineering Geology Practice)" was released. In Langen (Germany), at a Technical Construction Exhibition, a set of maps and texts considered the beginning of Engineering geological Mapping were presented. The texts brought points of view, still important today, as to the content and spatial representation, called charts, to support the development of the cities of Erfurt, Frankfurt, and Danzig.

The second book of Engineering Geology was published in 1914 by Ries and Watson was published, gaining a new version in 1921 called "Elements of Engineering Geology." In 1919, L.V. Pirsson released a paper entitled "Rock Classification for Engineering," and Josef Stini (Austria) published "Technische Geologie" (Engineering Geology) in 1922. Both are reference works for the time and are important in Engineering Geology's history. Between 1920 and 1930, maps were published in Russia to support the canal construction between the White and Baltic Seas and the Volga Right Bank Irrigation Project.

In Brazil, this period was marked by the construction of several engineering works such as tunnels, railroads, and dams. According to, Vargas (1985, 2001), the first document on Engineering Geology in Brazil date from 1907, about the Noroeste do Brasil Railroad.

Period between 1925 and 1950

In 1926 a set of engineering geological maps of Prague was published in former Czechoslovakia. In 1928, the first course in Engineering Geology was started at Columbia University; at this time, Charles Berkey was the first engineering geologist at the USBR.

In 1928, the St. Francis dam burst, in California (USA), which killed more than 450 people and caused losses of more than 9 million dollars, accelerated the implementation of Engineering Geology in the USA, with Charles Berkey as its exponent. At the same time,

Quido Zaruba, in former Czechoslovakia, and Popov, in Russia, were developing Engineering Geology in Eastern Europe.

In 1929 another book on Engineering Geology was released by Redlich, Terzaghi, and Kampe, as was K. Terzaghi published the text "Effect of minor geological details on the Safety of Dams," considered by many professionals as a classic work. M. Lugeon, in 1933, published "Barrages et Géologie". In 1934, the first engineering geological map for a large region of Russia was presented, which brought a new view on the technique and provided the orientation for other similar works in several countries. C.S. Fox, in 1935, published the book "A Comprehensive Treatise on Engineering Geology." In 1936, the First International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering was held. Between 1939 and 1943, two books were published: "Geology and Engineering" by Legget and Boswell and "Geology for Engineers" by Blyth.

In 1950, two landmark events were the release of the book "Techniques for Engineering Geological Mapping" by Popov (Russia) and the Berkey Volume, entitled Application of Geology to Engineering Practices (Geological Society), in honor of Charles Berkey, by S. Paige. In 1947, Hans Cloos published a book, "Conversation with the Earth," translated into English in 1953. In the same year, K. Zebera proposed the Band Method for the 3D representation of layers of geological materials. Also, George A. Kiersch created the Engineering Geology Division as the first operating division of the Geological Society of America, and K. Terzaghi published the book Engineering Geology.

Period between 1950 and 1970

In 1955, John Russell Schultz published the book "Geology in Engineering," which had many editions up to the end of the 1980s and is still an essential bibliographic reference. In 1957, the first graduate course in Engineering Geology was created at Imperial College (London, England), led by John Knill, and open to geologists and engineers. In Brazil, the first Geology courses were created at UFRGS, USP, UFRJ, UFPE, and UFOP. The Association of Engineering Geologists (AEG) was created in the USA. The book "Principles of Engineering Geology and Geotechnics" by Krynine and Judd was launched, addressing the relationship between Engineering Geology and Geotechnics.

In 1967 the Association of Engineering Geology(AEG) was founded to reach all the American states and outline the technical and ethical guidelines of the Engineering Geology professional. In the 1960s, in Eastern Europe, Milan Matula, considered one of the ten most

essential engineering geologists, stood out due to his work in almost all fronts of Engineering Geology.

In 1962, R.F. Legget published the book "Geology and Engineering." In 1963, Q. Zaruba and V. Mencl published the book "Engineering Geology." In 1964, the embryo of the International Association of Engineering Geology (IAEG) appeared, with the primary objectives of bringing together professionals from different countries and trying to homogenize technical procedures and the Engineering Geology group of the Geological Society.

A text on the Vaiont disaster was published by G.A. Kiersch (1965), entitled "The Vaiont Tragedy: geologic causes and engineering implications." In 1967, the First Congress of the International Society of Rock Mechanics was held, and between 1968 and 1969, several papers related to Engineering Geology were published by CSIRO (Australia). Milan Matula published a text entitled "Regional Engineering Geology of Czechoslovak Carpathians," which brought a new vision of Engineering Geology works for large territorial extensions. In 1968 the 23rd International Geological Congress took place in Prague and the first general assembly of the IAEG. Many papers related to Engineering Geology and engineering geological mapping were presented at this congress.

In Brazil, between 1950 and 1970, several Engineering Geology centers were started, mainly in the states of São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and Minas Gerais, with the implementation of large engineering and mining works. Haberlener was hired in 1956 to work with hydroelectric plants. He then went to work as a professor at UFRJ and published, in 1966, the work called Principles of Engineering Geological Mapping (the first work on Engineering Geological Mapping in Brazil), as well as a report for CNPQ on the slopes of the city of Rio de Janeiro (together with a group of professionals). Heine (1966) published the Geotechnical Survey of the Estado da Guanabara.

The teaching of Engineering Geology at UFRJ was started in 1967, and a subarea of Graduate Studies in 1968. In this period, Engineering Geology was developed at IPT, São Paulo, in the Applied Geology Section, founded in 1955, where Ernesto Pichler worked. In 1968, the Association of Applied Geology of the São Paulo state appeared, which, together with other groups, gave the basis for the Brazilian Association of Engineering Geology. The 1st Applied Geology Week was held in 1969. R. Glossop made a presentation, in 1969, on the theme "Engineering geology and soil mechanics," which is an exciting text for understanding the relationship between the two areas of knowledge.

In this period, it is worth remembering some professionals who were developing professional activities, in Brazil, as a tribute to all engineering geologists, such as Murilo Dondici Ruiz, Milton Kanji, Fernando Pires de Camargo, Guido Guidicini, Fernão Paes de Barros, Luiz Ferreira Vaz, Alfredo José Simon Bjorberg, Nivaldo Chiossi, Ronaldo Simões Lopes de Azambuja, Josué Alves Barroso, Sergio Brito, Antonio Manuel de Oliveira, and others.

Period between 1970 and 1980

Engineering Geology significantly expanded in this decade, reaching practically all countries. In 1970, the 1st International Congress of Engineering Geology was held in Paris, which is important because papers from hundreds of countries were presented. To this day, many are consulted for guidance in professional and research activities. In 1970, the Bulletin of the International Association of Engineering Geology was also released, and the first issue brought to the text by M. Arnould on the "International Association of Engineering Geology, History-Activity," with the statutes and other information, as well as papers on the stage of Engineering Geology in some countries.

Between 1971 and 1972, the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th Applied Geology Weeks of the Association of Applied Geology of the São Paulo state were held. Fred O. Jones published, in 1973, a study about the landslides of Rio de Janeiro and the Serra das Araras (association between DNPM and the Agency for International Development - USA), covering a history of the processes, as well as a general analysis of the conditioning factors and other anthropic aspects involved (Landslides of Rio de Janeiro and the Serra das Araras Escarpment, Brazil). The year 1974 was one of the most important years for Engineering Geology in Brazil, as the 2nd International Congress of Engineering Geology was held in the city of São Paulo, organized by the Brazilian Association of Engineering Geology (ABGE) and IAEG.

In the period between 1974 and 1976, the first IAEG Commission (Engineering Geological Mapping Commission - IAEGE) was created. The text "The Logic of engineering geological and related maps: A Discussion of the Definition and Classification of map units, with special references to problems presented by Maps Intended for Uses in civil engineering" by Varnes, was published. This text brought new aspects to be incorporated into engineering geological mapping work. In 1975 the 1st Brazilian Congress of Engineering Geology was held, and work began on the Itaipu Dam.

In 1976, a graduate course in Geotechnics was created at the São Carlos Engineering School (USP), which brought together the efforts of members of the Geotechnical Department and

the Engineering Geology Sector of the IPT. In 1978 the 3rd International Congress of Engineering Geology was held in Madrid, with a significant number of papers and following the same distribution as in São Paulo.

In 1970, the Geological Society of London published a text entitled "The logging of rock cores for engineering purposes" (prepared by J. L. Knill, C. R. Cratchley, K. R. Early, R. W. Gallois, J. D. Humphreys, J. Newbery, D. G. Price, and R. G. Thurrell), which underwent a revision in 1977, characterized as a fundamental text for teaching Engineering Geology.

In 1979 there were two meetings coordinated by IAEG, the "Engineering Geological Mapping Symposium, Newcastle upon Tyne," which can be considered one of the top ten sets of papers on engineering geological mapping, and a Commission Engineering Geological Mapping (IAEG) proposal on rock and soil classification (Classification of Rocks and Soils for Engineering Geological Mapping. Part 1: Rock and Soil Materials).

Period between 1980 and 1990

The 4th Brazilian Congress of Engineering Geology took place in Belo Horizonte (MG), with a theme and papers in the same direction as the previous one. The 5th International Congress of Engineering Geology (IAEG) was held in Buenos Ayres, always keeping the IAEG's goal of spreading Engineering Geology in different countries. In 1982, the IAEG held the 4th International Congress of Engineering Geology in the city of New Delhi, and the Geological Society of London published the text "Land Surface Evaluation for Engineering Practice (Report by a Working Party)," with guidelines and procedures that helped the development of geotechnical mapping in many countries.

In 1981, the AEG (USA) published the first edition of the Professional Practice Handbook (<http://www.aegweb.org/files/public/aegpph.pdf>), an introductory text for American engineering geologists but for Brazilians and other countries as well. This text still needs to be discovered in the Brazilian technical community.

In 1990, IAEG held its 6th International Congress of Engineering Geology in Amsterdam, the event with Brazilians' lowest participation among all IAEG congresses. On the other hand, ABGE and the Brazilian Association of Soil Mechanics (ABMS) sought to hold joint events. They had this year, in Salvador (BA), the 6th Brazilian Congress of Engineering Geology and the Brazilian Congress of Soil Mechanics and Foundations. The 1st Latin American Symposium on Urban Geological Hazards occurred in São Paulo (SP), driven mainly by the UN declaration of the International Decade of Risk Reduction.

In this period, computer resources enable the treatment of information more consistently and the use of mathematical models that allow greater efficiency of techniques such as geophysical and monitoring.

Period between 1990 and 2000

In 1991, there was an event and the publication of the text "The Heritage of Engineering Geology: The First hundred years" by G.A.Kiersch, which constitutes one of the complete texts about the evolution of Engineering Geology, in this case, for the USA. In the same year, the publication of Dearman's book "Engineering Geological Mapping" synthesized knowledge about engineering geological mapping, mainly from England and other classic works. In 1994, the 7th International Congress of Engineering Geology was held in Lisbon, with the most significant participation of Brazilians, not counting the one held in São Paulo in 1974.

The Engineering Geology completed 30 years at UFRJ. Barroso and Cabral prepared a special report about this area of knowledge, relating the aspects of implantation and the activities developed until then. In 1996, a technical-scientific meeting on uncertainty in the geological environment (Uncertainty in the Geologic Environment: From Theory to Practice) was held, which discussed the importance of assessing uncertainty in environmental and geotechnical projects. In 1997, Peter Fookes delivered the lecture as First Glossop Lecture, with the title "Geology for Engineers: the geological model, prediction and Performance," which deals with the relationships between geological information and engineering works and discusses several conceptual aspects of the different topics that are considered within the field of Geology and Geotechnics.

In 1998, the 8th International Congress of Engineering Geology was held in Vancouver (Canada), and, from then on, IAEG was renamed the International Association of Engineering Geology and the Environment (IAEGE) and the Engineering Geology Group (US Department of the Interior - Bureau of Reclamation) launched, in a limited edition, the Engineering Geology Field Manual (<http://www.usbr.gov/pmts/geology/geoman.html>), which is a text little known by the Brazilian technical environment, of excellent quality.

In 2000, a technical-scientific event took place in Australia involving IAEGE, the International Association of Rock Mechanics (ISRM), and International Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering (ISMEF), which discussed the meeting of the three primary areas of Geotechnics as a function of the term "Common Ground." In this event, a lecture was given

by Morgenstern under the title "Common Ground" and also another one by Fookes, Baynes, and Hutchinson on the theme "Total Geological History: A model approach to the Anticipation, observation, and Understanding of site conditions." Both are very interesting for professionals in Engineering Geology and Geotechnics in general.

As of the beginning of this decade, a significant number of professionals participated in work involving environmental aspects, reaching more than half of the professionals in many countries. Consequently, the term Environment was added to most national associations' denominations and IAEG, which became the International Association of Engineering Geology and the Environment (IAEGE).

Period between 2000 to present

IAEGE held, in 2002, the 9th International Congress on Geology and Engineering, in Durban (South Africa), with the central theme of Engineering Geology for developing countries. Knill (2002) held the lecture The First Hans-Cloos Lecture - Core Values for Engineering Geology, which led IAEGE to have discussions on the topic and, in 2004, published in IAEG News (Vol 32, No 1, 2004), a set of the issues considered as Core Values that guide the teaching and training of professionals:

- 1 - Site-specific (site or project-related) engineering geologic descriptions of stratigraphy, structure, groundwater, processes, and related engineering or environmental performance.*
- 2 - Universal engineering geologic summaries (applicable worldwide) of properties, parameters, and engineering performance of geologic materials or processes, soil/rock/water systems, and environmental systems, especially inhomogeneous and/or fractured materials and/or active processes.*
- 3 - Investigation and characterization methods, surface and subsurface field techniques, especially to investigate and describe spatial variability, capabilities, and limitations of investigation techniques.*
- 4 - Engineering geologic models as representations of site-specific and predicted engineering geologic conditions, preparation protocols, metadata requirements, descriptions of geologic uncertainty, model visualization, transformation methods in ground engineering models, use of models for risk management and geologic risk engineering*
- 5 - Engineering geologic information management and communication, reporting, engineering geologic terminology, defensible reporting standards, codes of practice, communication with end users, education, and training.*

Culshaw (2005) published the text "From Concept to towards reality: developing the attributed 3D geological model of the shallow subsurface", which addresses a fundamental theme for the understanding of the spatial variability of geological materials and geological structures, which gained new strength, in this decade, due to advances in computational techniques.

In 2006, the 10th International Congress of Engineering Geology and the Environment was held in Nottingham (England), with the central theme of Engineering Geology for the cities of the future, and some publications brought new ideas and debates. H. Bock's publication "Common Ground in engineering geology, soil mechanics and rock mechanics: past, present and future" points to future paths that the three primary areas of Geotechnics can follow. In 2009, the Geological Society of London published a special book (edited by M G Culshaw, H J Reeves, I Jefferson, and T Spink), entitled "Engineering Geology for Tomorrow's Cities," with texts by several authors, about the basis and future of Engineering Geology, with visions for different countries.

The 11th International Congress of Engineering Geology and the Environment (IAEGE) was held in Auckland (New Zealand), dealing predominantly with hazard, risk, and the future of Engineering Geology as an application science.

Among all the aspects that Engineering Geology has discussed in the last 10 years, two have predominated: Uncertainty assessments in predicting hazard events and associated risks, whether related to engineering works, recovery and prognosis of environmental problems or environmental problems natural processes, and 3D/4D model analysis.

In these 20 years, many books related to Engineering Geology have been published with contents related to new approaches and uses of technological, statistical, and mathematical resources, as seen in Table 1 before.

REFERENCES

AEG (1993). Professional Practice Handbook, 3rd Edition, Special Publication No.5 (eds) Brown & Proctor first edition, HooseS.N. 3rd edition.

AEG (2002). AEG News, Association of Engineering Geologists, Vol. 45, Annual Report and Directory, p 18.

Anon (1999). "Time to Investigate". Ground Engineering, magazine of British Geotechnical Society, Vol.32, No.11, pp 52-54.

- Anon. (2002). Key Issues in Earth Sciences: Vol. 1: Mapping in Engineering Geology. Geological Society Publishing House, London. Compiled by Griffiths, J., 294p.
- Anon. (2003). Code of Conduct, Geological Society of London, www.geolsoc.org.uk.
- Arnould, M. (1970). The International Association of Engineering Geology, History-Activity. Bulletin of the I.A.E.G. Vol. 1: pp 22-28.
- Baynes, F. J. (1999). Engineering Geological Knowledge and Quality, Proceedings of the Eight Australia New Zealand Conference on Geomechanics, Volume 1 Hobart, Institution of Engineers Australia, pp 227 – 234.
- Bell, F.G. (1983). Fundamentals of Engineering Geology. Butterworths.
- Bell, F.G. (2007). Basic Environmental and Engineering Geology. Whittles Publishing, 384p.
- CNPQ (1967) O movimento de encosta no Estado da Guanabara e regiões Circunvizinhas. Relatório da Comissão de especialistas, CNPQ/Presidência da Republica.
- de Freitas, M.H. (2004). Geology; its principles, practice and potential for Geotechnics. Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology (2009), 42 (4): 397.
- Dearman, W.R. (1971). Introductory statement to regional meeting of the Engineering Group of the Geological Society Dublin. Q. Jl Eng. Geol Vol. 4, No.3, pp 187-190.
- Fell, R (1995). Geotechnical education, Australian Geomechanics. No 27, pp 26-28.
- Fookes, P.G., Baynes F.J., & Hutchinson, J.H. (2001). Total geological history: a model approach to understanding site conditions, Ground Engineering, Magazine of British Geotechnical Society Vol.34, No 3, pp 42-47.
- Gonzalez de Vellejo, L., & Ferrer, M. (2011). Geological Engineering. CRC Press.
- Hall, J. (1839). Classification of "Slate rock and shale," Erie Canal Locks Construction, Lockport, New York: New York. Geological Survey Annual Report, p.287-339.
- Heine, D.H. (1966). Levantamento geotécnico do Estado da Guanabara. In: CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE GEOLOGIA, 22, 1966, Rio de Janeiro. Resumos ... Rio de Janeiro: SBG. p.41. (Boletim, 1).
- Hoek, E., & Palmieri A. (1998). Geotechnical risks on large civil engineering projects. 8th International Congress of I.A.E.G., Vancouver, Canada, 21-25 September, Vol.1, pp 79-88.
- ISRM (1983). Report of the Commission on the Teaching of Rock Mechanics. In: International Journal of Rock Mechanics, Mining Sciences & Geomechanics Abstracts, v. 20, n. 4, Pergamon Press, Cambridge, pp. 189-200.
- James, L.B., & Kiersch, G.A. (1991). Failures of engineering works. The Heritage of Engineering Geology; The First Hundred Years, Geological Society of American, Centennial Special Vol. 3, pp 481-516.

Jones, F. O. (1973). Landslides of Rio de Janeiro and the Serra das Araras escarpment, Brazil. Professional paper Geological Survey (U.S.), no. 697, p.43.

Judd, W.R., (1967). Geotechnical Communication Problems; Alex L. du Toit Memorial Lectures No.10. The Geological Society South Africa, annexure to Vol. 70, 45p.

Katzenbach, R., & Bachmann, G. (2004). Some basic considerations about the necessities and possibilities of cooperation between civil engineers and engineering geologists. In: Engineering Geology for Infrastructure Planning in Europe. A European Perspective. Springer, Berlin, pp. 9-14.

Kiersch, G.A. (1955). Engineering geology. Quarterly of the Colorado School of Mines, vol 30, 122 pp

Kiersch, G.A. (1991). "The heritage of engineering geology; Changes through time". The Heritage of Engineering Geology; The First Hundred Years, ed. by G.A. Kiersch, Centennial Special Volume 3, Geological Society of America, p. 1-50.

Kiersch G.A., & James L.B. (1991). Errors of geological judgment and the impact on engineering works. The Heritage of Engineering Geology; The First Hundred Years, Geological Society of American, Centennial Special, Vol.3, pp 517-558.

Knill, J. L., Cratchley C. R., Early K. R., Gallois R. W., Humphreys J. D., Newbery J., Price D. G., & Thurrell R. G. (1970) Geological Society Engineering Group Working Party report on the logging of rock cores for engineering purposes. *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology* December 1970, v. 3:1-24.

Legget, R.F., & Karrow, P.F. (1983). Handbook of Geology in Civil Engineering. McGraw-Hill.

Matula, M. (1969). Regional engineering geology of Czechoslovak Carpathians. Published by Vyd. Slov. akad. vied, Bratislava, 221 pp.

Norbury, D. (2004). Current issues relating to the professional practice of engineering geology in Europe. In: Engineering Geology for Infrastructure Planning in Europe. A European Perspective. Springer, Berlin, pp. 15-30.

Oliveira, R. (1986). Geologia de engenharia e mecânica das rochas. Conceitos fundamentais. Metodologia de estudo de maciços rochosos. Proc. II Simpósio Sul Americano de Mecânica das Rochas, Porto Alegre, v. 1, pp. 203-214.

Oliveira, R. (1995). Geotechnical education at graduate level. 18 years of experience at the New University of Lisbon. Proc. XI European Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering, Copenhagen, pp. 6151-6155.

Rengers, N., Hack, R., Huisman, M., Slob, S., & Zigterman, W. (2002). Information Technology Applied to Engineering Geology. 9th International Congress of I.A.E.G., South Africa, 16-20 September, (eds) van Rooy, J.L. & Jermy C.A. pp 83-105, South African Institute of Engineering and Environmental Geologists.

Stapledon, D.H. (1982). Subsurface engineering – in search of a rational approach. Australian Geomechanics News, Vol. 4, pp 26 – 33.

Stapledon, D.H. (1983). Towards Successful Waterworks, Proceedings Symposium for Dams and Canals, Alexandra, Institution of Professional Engineers, New Zealand, pp 1.3 – 1.15.

Stapledon, D. (1986). Let's Keep the "Geo" in Geomechanics. Specialty Geomechanics Symposium, Adelaide, 18-19 August 1986, pp 18-31.

Stapledon, D.H. (1996). Keeping the “Geo”; Why and How, the John Jaeger Memorial Address, Proceedings of the Seventh Australia New Zealand Conference on Geomechanics, Adelaide, South Australia, Jaksa, Kaggwa & Cameron (eds), Institution of Engineers, Australia, Canberra, pp3-18.

Vallejo, L.G. (2010). “JTC3 Education And Training In Geo-Engineering Final Report Of Activities 2006 – 2009.Submitted to Federation Of The International Geo-Engineering Societies (FedIGS).

Vargas, M (1985). Origem e desenvolvimento da Geotecnologia no Brasil. Quipu, Vol. 2.

Vargas, M. (2001). História da ciência e da tecnologia no Brasil: uma súmula / Milton Vargas. – São Paulo : Humanitas / FFLCH / USP : Centro Interunidade de História da Ciência, 2001. 146 p

Zaruba, Q. (1970). Engineering geology, some experiences and considerations. Bulletin of the International Association of Engineering Geology, No. 1, p. 15-21.

Zebera, K. (1947). Geologie in der regionalenplanung. Geotechnica, vol. 4, Praha.

CURRENT THEMES IN ENGINEERING GEOLOGY TEACHING

The main subjects offered in Engineering Geology disciplines, aimed at engineering courses at universities in different countries, taken from different references and texts published since the beginning of the 20th century are shown in following Table 2.

Table 2. Main topics currently covered in Engineering Geology disciplines taught in different countries.

Topics	Themes	Contents	Approach	Aspects that must be considered in both the theoretical and practical approach
1	General concepts	Geology, Applied geology, Engineering geology, Geotechnics	T	Present the conceptual aspects and the application of knowledge in different aspects of civil works and Civil Engineering.
2	Engineering geology and Geotechnics	Integration of Engineering Geology, Soil and Rock Mechanics.	T	Present the different interactions between the 3 areas of Geotechnics.
3	The Earth and its divisions	Earth Structures, Lithosphere, Geological Materials and others. Regolith and bedrock.	T	P A general overview of the Earth's structure, geological materials, and the relationships with the three major areas of geotechnics to facilitate understanding of the following topics in the discipline.
4	Minerals	Mineral classes and how intrinsic characteristics affect geotechnical properties as well as uses. The focus is on phyllosilicates.	T	P Mainly the observation of mineral types and the relationships with the properties and uses of geological materials for civil construction and rheological relationships.
5	Rock	Igneous, sedimentary and metamorphic rocks. Characterization and classifications. Estimation of properties.	T	P Fundamentally, the practical classes address the identification of the rock type, the observation of the degree of alteration, and from the intrinsic characteristics, explore the classifications and estimates of rheological properties and behavior.

6	Geological Structures, Stratigraphic rules and Earthquakes	Concepts of stratigraphy and application to construction sites. Faults, folds, fractures and other types of discontinuities. Earthquake occurrence and importance to engineering works.	T	P	Associate the principles of stratigraphy, stratigraphic units and relief. The main types of geological structures (tectonic, genetic and resulting from geological processes) and their interaction with some types of works. The concepts involved in earthquakes, spatial distribution, types of waves generated and the classifications of magnitude and intensity.
7	Unconsolidated materials: transported and residual. Weathering. Mineralogy.	Weathering concepts and types. Materials resulting from weathering. Origin of residual and transported unconsolidated materials. Spatial distribution.	T	P	Consider the processes of genesis of different unconsolidated materials and their mineralogy and relationships with geotechnical properties.
8.1	Geotechnical properties and physical and geological characteristics	The relationships between geological and physical characteristics intrinsic to different groups of geological materials and geotechnical properties.	T	P	Addressing genetic and evolutionary characteristics of rock and unconsolidated materials that condition physical and chemical properties. Characteristics that are used in the different classifications.
8.2	Classifications of regolith profiles, soils, saprolites, and weathered rocks.	Principles and conditions of the different classifications and uses.	T	P	Consider the principles of each classification and purpose. Applications of the classifications.
9	Water	Relationship between surface and subsurface water. Unsaturated and saturated zone. Drainage and lowering of the saturated zone. Types of aquifers.	T	P	Developing an understanding of the importance of the relationship between surface and subsurface water in relation to environmental conditions. The conditions between the saturated and unsaturated zone and its relationship with the works and aquifer recharge. The constraints that positively and negatively interfere with the choice of resources for saturated zone lowering.

10	Geological processes: Interaction with the works and as a source of risk.	Geological fundamentals and conditioning factors of the most frequent processes: erosion, gravitational mass movements, karst, flooding, silting.	T	P	Point out how engineering works can be affected by these processes, as well as their ability to modify the environment and accelerate the occurrence of these processes.
11	Regional and detailed geology	Lesson on the geology of the country, state and city.	T	P	To provide a view at different scales of the geological aspects in which the school is inserted, from the regional to the local. To relate existing civil works to geological variations.
12	Field trip	A trip lasting a few days to a region with a diversity of geological materials, structures, and geological processes.	T	P	The first educational trip aims at contacting different geological materials, structures, geological processes and visiting works in execution and in operation.
13	Models: geological and conceptual	Concepts and methods and procedures for development. Importance for planning geological - geotechnical investigations, as well as the conceptual model and its applications.	T	P	Based on existing geological and geotechnical maps, geological models are developed to guide the development and aspects of investigations.
13.1	Geological maps	Spatial arrangement of geological materials and structures.	T	P	How maps can be used in the planning and feasibility analysis of a construction project, considering the spatial distribution of the geological materials represented on the maps. Development of vertical profiles. Calculation of thickness, depth, dip and angle relations between alignments and planes.
13.2	Engineering geological/geotechnical maps	Use of engineering geological/geotechnical maps as a source of data in the implementation of engineering works and solution of environmental problems.	T	P	The use of engineering geological/geotechnical maps at detailed scales in the case of point works and at regional scales for longitudinal works, land planning and control of environmental problems, as well as watershed studies and water resources.

14	Geological materials as different construction materials (aggregates, etc.)	Unconsolidated materials such as embankment material, fine aggregates, filters, and protection barriers. Rock materials such as ornamental stones, coarse aggregate, railroad ballast, riprap, armor, gabions. Field and laboratory tests.	T	P	Addressing favorable and unfavorable characteristics of the geological materials for different uses. Field and laboratory tests and analysis of results.
15	Rock Excavation/Rock blasting (excavation/dismantling)	Types and constructive aspects, purposes, and favorable and unfavorable geological conditions.	T	P	The different favorable and unfavorable aspects. Possible geotechnical problems that can occur and control and corrective measures.
	Foundation		T	P	
	Dams		T	P	
	Embankments		T	P	
	Tunnel		T	P	
	Roads		T	P	
	Slopes		T	P	
	Hydraulic Structures		T	P	
16	Environmental problems	Contamination of geological materials and waters. Siltation. Subsidence.	T	P	The geological and geotechnical characteristics that control the flow of contaminants in geological porous media. The conditions for the execution of works in areas consisting of geological materials with high erodibility and geological materials that can generate subsidence.
17	Field trip	The aim of the trip is to use maps in the field, visit construction sites, and observe environmental problems. Visits to sources of construction materials.	T	P	The second trip aims to put the students in touch with the various geological conditions recorded on maps that construction sites have been built on, as well as of demands for construction materials.

18	Geological and geotechnical investigation	Introduce the different methods and the technological resources associated with each type. Limitations and advantages of the types. Geological conditions x types of investigations.	T	P	To introduce the use and treatment of results from different methods and procedures of geological-geotechnical investigation and their uses in construction and environmental problems.
19	Geological discontinuities	Concepts, types and characterization.	T	P	The importance of the different types of discontinuities in the evaluation of rock and earth masses. Analysis of the characteristics that evaluate the potential geomechanical behaviors.
20	Rock mass classifications	Addressing aspects of engineering geology in the different classifications and uses.	T	P	Addressing the use of geomechanical classifications for rock mass parameterization. Application examples of GSI and Bieniawski classifications.
21	Field trip	Didactic field trip to observe the application of geological - geotechnical investigation techniques and field practice to identify and characterize discontinuities.	T	P	Practical activities of rock mass characterization and use of geomechanical classification.
22	Gravitational mass movements in rock	Kinematic and dynamic analysis. Use of specific software for data processing using stereonet.	T	P	The use of kinematic and dynamic analysis in the evaluation of the stability of specific slopes and the treatment of discontinuity data.
23	Slope stability assessments and monitoring in active open-pit mines;	Methods and procedures for evaluating open pit mine slopes. Monitoring procedures.	T	P	Application of engineering geology aspects to the stability analysis of excavated slopes in open-pit mines.
24	Models in Geotechnics	Aspects of the engineering geology that condition the	T	P	Development of a model to be used in a construction site and considering the purpose

		different domains, considering the uses (slopes, foundation, etc.)		(kinematic, empirical, numerical, etc.)
25	Engineering geology applied in offshore areas	Methods and procedures of engineering geology investigation in offshore areas for geological-geotechnical characterization.	T	P Offshore structures and geological and geotechnical demands. Data analysis obtained for offshore areas.
26	Terrain models and 3D and 4D analysis	Data entropy and uncertainty. Application to mining and roads. Application of geostatistics. Programs.	T	P Development of 3D terrain models and application of statistics resources in geotechnical data analysis.

EXPERIENCES DEVELOPED IN THE GEOTECHNICAL DEPARTMENT/SÃO CARLOSSCHOOL OF ENGINEERING/UNIVERSITY OF SÃO PAULO (EESC/USP)

The following Tables show the main topics taught in the Geotechnical Department for Civil and Environmental Engineering Courses at São Carlos School of Engineering (EESC/USP) from 1960 to now.

Table 3 . Subjects taught in Civil Engineering from 1960 to 2000 at the São Carlos School of Engineering, EESC/USP.

Topics	Themes	Contents	Approach
1	General concepts	Geology, Applied geology, Engineering geology, Geotechnics	T
2	Engineering geology and Geotechnics	Integration of Engineering Geology, Soil and Rock Mechanics.	T
3	The Earth and its divisions	Earth Structures, Lithosphere, Geological Materials and others. Regolith and bedrock.	T P
4	Minerals	Mineral classes and how intrinsic characteristics affect geotechnical properties as well as uses. Focus on phyllosilicates.	T P
5	Rock	Igneous, sedimentary and metamorphic rocks. Characterization and classifications. Estimation of properties.	T P
6	Geological Structures, Stratigraphic rules and Earthquakes	Concepts of stratigraphy and application to construction sites. Faults, folds, fractures and other types of discontinuities. Earthquake occurrence and importance for engineering works.	T P
7	Unconsolidated materials and	Weathering concepts and types. Materials resulting from weathering. Spatial	T P

	Weathering.	distribution.	
8	Classifications of soils	Principles and conditions of the different classifications and uses.	T P
9	Regional and detailed geology	Lesson on the geology of the country, state and city.	T P
10	Field trip	A trip lasting a few days to a region with a diversity of geological materials, structures, and geological processes.	T P
11	Geological maps	Spatial arrangement of geological materials and structures.	T P
12	Geological materials, such as different construction materials (aggregates, etc.)	Unconsolidated materials such as embankment material, fine aggregates, filters, and protection barriers. Rock materials such as ornamental stones, coarse aggregate, railroad ballast, riprap, armor, gabions, ... Field and laboratory tests.	T P
13	Rock Excavation/Rock blasting (excavation/dismantling)	Types and constructive aspects, purposes, and favorable and unfavorable geological conditions.	T P

	Foundation		T	P
	Dams		T	P
	Embankments		T	P
	Tunnel		T	P
	Roads		T	P
	Slopes		T	P
14	Field trip	The aim of the trip is to use maps in the field, visit construction sites, and observe environmental problems. Visits to sources of construction materials.	T	P
15	Geological and geotechnical investigation	Introduce the different methods and the technological resources associated with each type. Limitations and advantages of the types. Geological conditions x types of investigations.	T	P
16	Geological discontinuities	Concepts, types and characterization.	T	P
17	Rock mass classifications	Addressing aspects of engineering geology in the different classifications and uses.	T	P
18	Field trip	Didactic field trip to observe the application of geological - geotechnical investigation techniques and field practice to identify and characterize discontinuities.	T	P
19	Gravitational mass movements in rock	Kinematic and dynamic analysis. Using specific software for data processing applying a stereogram.	T	P

Table 4. Topics (from: Table 2) were inserted in the third phase.

Topics	Themes	Contents	Approach	Aspects that must be considered in both the theoretical and practical approach
1	Geotechnical properties and physical and geological characteristics	The relationships between geological and physical characteristics intrinsic to different groups of geological materials and geotechnical properties.	T P	Addressing genetic and evolutionary characteristics of rock and unconsolidated materials that condition physical and chemical properties. Characteristics that are used in the different classifications.
2	Classifications of regolith profiles: saprolites, and weathered rocks.	Principles and conditions of the different classifications and uses.	T P	Consider the principles of each classification and the purpose. Applications of the classifications.
3	Water	Relationship between surface and subsurface water. Unsaturated and saturated zone. Drainage and lowering of the saturated zone. Types of aquifers.	T P	Developing an understanding of the importance of the relationship between surface and subsurface water in relation to environmental conditions. The conditions between the saturated and unsaturated zone and its relationship with the works and aquifer

				recharge. The constraints that positively and negatively interfere in the choice of resources for saturated zone lowering.
4	Models: geological and conceptual	Concepts and methods and procedures for development. Importance for planning geological - geotechnical investigations, as well as the conceptual model and its applications.	T P	Based on existing geological and geotechnical maps, geological models are developed to guide the development and aspects of investigations.
5	Geological materials as different construction materials	Rock materials such as railroad ballast, riprap, armor, gabions, ... Field and laboratory tests.	T P	Addressing favorable and unfavorable characteristics of the geological materials for different uses. Field and laboratory tests and analysis of results.
6	Hydraulic Structures	Geological constraints that must be considered in the design and importance of the scale of observation of the data.	T P	The different favorable and unfavorable aspects. Possible geotechnical problems that can occur and control and corrective measures.
7	Terrain models and 3D and 4D analysis	Data entropy and uncertainty. Application to mining and roads. Application	T P	Development of 3D terrain models and application of statistics resources in the

		of geostatistics. Programs.		geotechnical data analysis.
--	--	--------------------------------	--	-----------------------------

Table 5. Topics are being integrated into Engineering Geology disciplines of engineering courses.

Topics	Themes	Contents	Approach	Aspects that must be considered in both the theoretical and practical approach
1	Geological processes: Interaction with the works and as a source of risk.	Geological fundamentals and conditioning factors of the most frequent processes: erosion, gravitational mass movements, karst, flooding, silting.	T P	Point out how engineering works can be affected by these processes, as well as their ability to modify the environment and accelerate the occurrence of these processes.
2	Engineering geological/geotechnical maps	Use of engineering geological/geotechnical maps as a source of data in the implementation of engineering works and solution of environmental problems.	T P	The use of engineering geological/geotechnical maps at detailed scales in the case of point works and at regional scales for longitudinal works, land planning and control of environmental problems, as well as watershed studies and water resources.
3	Environmental problems	Contamination of geological materials and. Siltation. Subsidence.	T P	The geological and geotechnical characteristics that control the flow of contaminants in geological porous media. The conditions for the execution of works in areas consisting of geological materials with

				high erodibility and geological materials that can generate subsidence.
4	Slope stability assessments and monitoring in active open-cast mines;	Methods and procedures for evaluating open pit mine slopes. Monitoring procedures.	T P	Application of engineering geology aspects to the stability analysis of excavated slopes in open-pit mines.
5	Models in Geotechnics	Aspects of the engineering geology that condition the different domains, considering the uses (slopes, foundation, etc...)	T P	Development of a model for use in a construction site and considering the purpose (kinematic, empirical, numerical, etc.)
6	Engineering geology applied in offshore areas	Methods and procedures of engineering geology investigation in offshore areas for geological-geotechnical characterization.	T P	Offshore structures and geological and geotechnical demands. Analysis of data obtained for offshore areas.

Figure 1. Relationship among the subjects of engineering geology and other disciplines in the Civil Engineering course of the EESC-USP.

Figure 2. Relationship among the subjects of engineering geology and other disciplines in the Environmental Engineering course at EESC-USP.